

Comparison of NCP with famous RNNs on specific datasets

Atabay Bashimov ¹, Xu Cheng ²

^{1,2}College of Computer Science, Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology, Nanjing, Jiangsu, 210044, P.R. China

Abstract: A wide range of issues involving sequence data have been solved using recurrent neural networks with various types of hidden units. One of the most recent proposals, neural circuit policies (NCP), has shown comparable promising results on our example datasets. In this paper, we compare three model variants of recurrent neural networks (RNN) with neural circuit policies (NCP), which is a subclass of continuous-time RNNs, with varying neuronal time-constant realized by their nonlinear synaptic transmission model. These four model variants, Deep RNN, LSTM, GRU, and NCP, were tested on synthetic sinusoidal training example sequences and the navigation of a robot dataset. The NCP model has shown similar performance to the SimpleRNN model while using fewer parameters and thus lowering training expense, and thus may be used as an alternate to the SimpleRNN recurrent neural network. However, in terms of lowest loss, LSTM and GRU performed slightly better than SimpleRNN and NCP on the datasets considered.

Keywords: recurrent neural networks (RNN); neural circuit policies (NCP); long short-term memory (LSTM); gated recurrent unit (GRU).

Accepted: 15 May, 2022; **Published:** 21 May, 2022

How to cite this article: Atabay Bashimov, Xu Cheng (2022). Comparison of NCP with famous RNNs on specific datasets. *North American Academic Research*, 5(5), 1-10. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569909>

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

RNNs (recurrent neural networks) are a form of neural network design used to find patterns in a series of data. Handwriting, genes, language, and quantitative time series are examples of such data that are frequently created in industry. Images, on the other hand, can be deconstructed into a number of patches and handled as a sequence [1]. RNNs are used in Language Modeling and Text Generation, Voice Recognition, Image Caption Generation, and Video Labeling at a higher level. The method through which information is transported through the network distinguishes Recurrent Neural Networks from Feedforward Neural Networks, also known as Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs). The RNN has cycles and sends data back into itself, whereas Feedforward Networks transfer information across the network without cycling. This allows them to expand the capabilities of Feedforward Networks to include earlier inputs in addition to the present one. Recurrent neural networks include some types such as Simple RNN, LSTM [2], and GRU [3]. RNNs have indeed been presented as a solution to difficult sequence issues like machine translation [4] and video captioning [5]. RNNs have recently been applied to handle issues involving spatial sequence [6], 2D image sequence [7], and spatial-temporal sequence [8]. Authors of [9] took inspiration from the neural calculations known to occur in real brains to progress towards a single, task-specific algorithm that fundamentally meets the representation-learning problems and attain a surprising degree of manoeuvrability. They created neural circuit policies (NCPs), which are concise models with greater computation power compared to current deep models. Evaluating these models before considering one of them for a certain task or certain dataset is a very crucial task in the deep learning field. To handle particular deep learning challenges, we can choose a suitable model based on performance, accuracy, and other factors. Papers such as [10] compare the performance of LSTM and GRU networks on quantitative time series data problems.

Deep RNNs have also been used to classify time series; see, for example, [11, 12]. On certain complicated sequences to be learnt and predicted, we use experiments to acquire insights into the differences between the NCP and popular RNNs. This research was influenced in part by: [13] who evaluate the performance of LSTM and GRU cells via extensive tests on low complexity and high complexity sequences; [14] who evaluate the performance of many variants of LSTM cells via extensive tests with three benchmark problems; and [15] who evaluate three variants of the Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) in recurrent neural networks (RNN) by reducing parameters in the update and reset gates, all rather different from our navigating a robotic vehicle around obstacles task. In this paper, we focus on the NCP and compare it with three types of RNNs. We comparatively evaluate the performance of the NCP, SimpleRNN, LSTM, and GRU on two datasets. Using the synthetic sinusoidal training Comparison of NCP with famous RNNs on specific datasets example, whose length of time series is equal to 48, we fed our training example, and after optimizing all models, we compared these models with each other. Then we did the same with these models by employing the navigating a robot dataset where we optimized all models in order to achieve low loss and compared them with each other not only in terms of low loss but also in terms of sparsity and number of parameters.

2. Methodology

In this section, we analyze and discuss four different forms of Recurrent Neural Networks. Deep RNN is discussed in Section 2.1, LSTM in Section 2.2, GRU in Section 2.3, and NCPs in Section 2.4.

2.1 Deep RNN

We may build Deep Recurrent Neural Networks (DRNNs) by stacking multiple layers of recurrent cells. Every hidden variable $H_t^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times h}$ is transferred to the present layer's subsequent time step and the following layer's current moment phase $H_{t+1}^{(l)}$. The hidden state is computed as indicated in Equation $H_t^{(l+1)}$ for the very first layer, and the hidden state from the previous layer is utilized as inputs for the succeeding layer [16].

$$H_t^{(1)} = \phi_1(X_t, H_{t-1}^{(1)})$$

$$H_t^{(l)} = \phi_l(H_t^{(l-1)}, H_{t-1}^{(l)})$$

The outcome $O_t \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times o}$, wherein o is the amount of outputs, is then calculated using just the hidden state of layer L , as indicated in Equation below.

$$O_t = \phi_o(H_t^{(L)} W_{ho} + b_o)$$

SimpleRNN has a serious problem: even though theoretically it should be able to store at any time information about input data viewed many time steps before, such long-term dependencies turn out to be impossible to study in practice. This is due to the vanishing gradient problem, an effect that is similar to what is observed in feedforward networks that have multilevel depth: as you continue to add layers to the network, the network eventually becomes untrainable. In the early 1990s, researchers such as Bengio, Hochreiter, and Schmidhuber studied the theoretical causes of the effect [17].

2.2 LSTM

To accurately handle the vanishing gradient problem, long-term short-term memory (LSTM) blocks were constructed. Step Hochreiter and Jurgen Schmidhuber [18] introduced it in 1997, and other scholars, including Alex Graves, Hashim Sak [19], and Wojciech Zaremba [20], have gradually enhanced it over the years. They allow RNN to be trained in a substantially higher number of time steps (over 1000) since they employ more constant mistakes [21]. To do this, LSTMs use structures called gated cells to store extra information outside of the usual neural network flow. The $i_{(t)}$ output element is used to read cell records, the $f_{(t)}$ input element is used to read data into the cell, and the forgot $o_{(t)}$ element is used to reset the cell contents in LSTM. Equations 13, 14, and 15 illustrate the results of the calculations for these equations.

$$i_{(t)} = \sigma(W_{xi}^T x_{(t)} + W_{hi}^T h_{(t-1)} + b_i)$$

$$f_{(t)} = \sigma(W_{xf}^T x_{(t)} + W_{hf}^T h_{(t-1)} + b_f)$$

$$o_{(t)} = \sigma(W_{xo}^T x_{(t)} + W_{ho}^T h_{(t-1)} + b_o)$$

The weight matrices of every one of the four layers for their relationship to the input $x_{(t)}$ are W_{xi} , W_{xf} , W_{xo} , W_{xg} , W_{hi} , W_{hf} , W_{ho} and W_{hg} are the weight matrices of each of the four layers in relation to the previous short-term state $h_{(t-1)}$.

The bias terms for every one of the four layers are b_i , b_f , b_o and b_g . The output signals of gateway controllers vary from 0 to 1 since they employ the logistic activation function. As we can see, their output data is sent to element-wise multiplication operations. Hence, the gate closes when the equation gives us 0s and opens otherwise (1s).

Next, we'll need a new memory cell $g_{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times h}$ that employs a *tanh* activation function to produce an output $\in (-1,1)$ instead of the previously specified gates. It also has its own $W_{(xg)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times h}$, $W_{(hg)} \in \mathbb{R}^{h \times h}$, and $b_g \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times h}$ biases. Equation below depicts the corresponding computation:

$$g_{(t)} = \tanh(W_{xg}^T x_{(t)} + W_{hg}^T h_{(t-1)} + b_g)$$

To connect the dots, we add old memory data $c_{(t-1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times h}$, which, in conjunction with the introduced gates, determines how much of the old memory content we want to save in order to access the new memory data c_t . Equation below shows this, where $\otimes$ signifies element-wise multiplication.

$$c_{(t)} = f_{(t)} \otimes c_{(t-1)} + i_{(t)} \otimes g_{(t)}$$

The final stage is to incorporate the $y_{(t)} = h_{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times h}$ hidden layer calculation into the architecture. Equation below illustrates this point.

$$y_{(t)} = h_{(t)} = o_{(t)} \otimes \tanh(c_{(t)})$$

We use the function to guarantee that every $h_{(t)}$ component is $\in (-1,1)$.

2.3 GRU

In a 2014 paper [22], Kyunghyun Cho et al. presented a cell featuring a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU). The GRU cell is a simplified form of the LSTM cell that appears to perform similarly to the LSTM cell [23]. As a result, its recognition is increasing year after year. The following are the most important simplifications:

- To create h_t^j , the state vectors are put together.
- The same gate controller controls both the forgetting gate and the input gate, z_t^j . The forget gate is accessible (= 1) and also the input input is shut ($1 - 1 = 0$) if the gate controller returns a value of 1. If it returns a value of 0, the result is the inverse. To put it another way, anytime memory must be saved, the location where it will be saved is deleted first. In reality, this is a common variation of the LSTM cell.
- Each time step sends the complete state vector; there is no output gate. However, a new gate controller, r_t^j , regulates which part of the prior state is shown to the main layer $\hat{h}_t^j$.

The gated recurrent units (GRU) [24, 25] simplify the gated RNN down to two gates: an update gate z_t and a reset gate r_t . The update gate controls how much the unit updates its j -th activation state h_t^j :

$$h_t^j = ((1 - z_t) \otimes h_{t-1} + z_t \otimes h_t^j)$$

The reset gate controls the amount of history used to update the candidate activation $\hat{h}_t^j$, and would essentially become dependent on only the external signal when it is close to zero. Specifically,

$$\hat{h}_t^j = \tanh(U(r_t \otimes h_{t-1}) + Wx_t + b)^j$$

The two gate equations, which are replicas of sRNN using the logistic function σ , have their own adaptive parameters as expressed in:

$$z_t^j = \sigma(U_z h_{t-1} + W_z x_t + b_z)^j$$

$$r_t^j = \sigma(U_r h_{t-1} + W_r x_t + b_r)^j$$

Thus, the GRU RNN increases the adaptive parameters by approximately three-folds in comparison to the sRNN. One of the key reasons for RNNs' effectiveness is the use of LSTM and GRU cells. Despite the fact that they can analyze considerably longer sequences than basic RNNs, they still have poor short-term memory, finding it challenging for them to retain long-term patterns in sequences of 100 or more time steps, such as audio recordings, extended time series, or long texts. One technique to overcome this challenge is to use 1D convolutional layers to minimize the input sequences.

2.4 NCP (LTC neurons)

Recurrent neural networks with a liquid time constant (LTC) [26] are a subtype of continuous time RNNs that use a nonlinear model of synaptic transmission to achieve a changeable time constant of synapses. This enables the model to simulate a continuous mapping with only a few processing units. The internal state of hidden units and n output units of the LTC network may mimic any finite path of an n -dimensional continuously complex system.

The following is a matrix representation of the entire system behaviors of LTC RNNs using $u(t) = [u_1(t), \dots, u_{n+N}(t)]^T$ expressing the internal states of N interneurons which are hidden neurons as well as n motor cells which are output neurons:

$$\dot{u}(t) = -(1/\tau + W\sigma(u(t)))u(t) + A + W\sigma(u(t))B$$

Wherein $\sigma(x)$ is C^1 - element-by-element application of sigmoid functions. $\tau^{n+N} > 0$ all synaptic time-constants are included, A is a $n + N$ sleeping phases vectors, B shows a $n + N$ neural reversals vectors, and W is a $n + N$ vector generated by the matrix multiplication of a weight vector of size $(n + N) \times (n + N)$ and an vector $n + N$ including the value reversal of all C_{m_i} s. Both A and B inputs are restricted to a specific number $[-\alpha, \beta]$ For $0 < \alpha < +\infty$, and $0 \leq \beta < +\infty$. A includes every V_{leak_i}/C_{m_i} And B shows all E_{ij} s.

When coupled by an incoming synapse to a neuron j (ref. 11), an NCP[9] is formed by a group of LTC cells, each of which has state dynamics $x_i(t)$, which are expressed as follows:

$$\dot{x}_i = -(1/\tau_i + w_{ij}/C_{m_i}\sigma_i(x_j))x_i + (x_{leak_i}/\tau_i + w_{ij}/C_{m_i}\sigma_i(x_j)E_{ij})$$

wherein $\tau_i = C_{m_i}/g_{l_i}$ denotes the cell's time constant with a leaking resistance of g_{l_i} , w_{ij} is a neural weight from neuron i to j , C_{m_i} is the membranes capacitor, $\sigma_i(x_j(t)) = 1/(1 + e^{-\gamma_{ij}(x_j - \mu_{ij})})$, x_{leak_i} is the sleeping potential, as well as E_{ij} is a reversal neural potential which determines the synapse's orientation. [26] defines the total connection sensitivity (time constant) of an LTC cell:

$$\tau_{system_i} = 1/((1/\tau_i) + (w_{ij}/C_{m_i})\sigma_i(x_j)).$$

For a few of cells in the controlling NCP [9], this dynamic time constant dictates how fast a neuron reacts throughout decision-making operations. All of the model's variables can be altered.

In conclusion, they use a semi-implicit Euler technique with a constant iterations for each neuron, as follows:

$$x_i(t + \Delta) := (x_i(t)C_{m_i}/\Delta + g_{l_i}x_{leak_i}\sum_{j \in I_{in}} w_{ij}\sigma_i(x_j(t))E_{ij}) / (C_{m_i}/\Delta + g_{l_i} + \sum_{j \in I_{in}} w_{ij}\sigma_i(x_j(t))),$$

The presynaptic synapses for cell i are represented by the set I_{in} . The fundamental Euler formula was used to get this equation:

$$x_i(t + \Delta) := x(t) + \Delta \cdot f(x(t + \tau), u(t + 1))$$

by assigning $\tau = \Delta$ for every $x(t + \tau)$ which look linear in the nonlinearity f , and assigning $\tau = 0$ for every another encounters. By adjusting $\tau = 0$, we can get the well-known direct (forward) Euler technique using formula. When establishing $\tau = \Delta$ and calculating the ensuing formula for $x(t + \Delta)$, the implied (backward) Euler technique is accomplished.

3. Experiments and results

On sequences created by synthetic sinusoidal training example, we conducted an empirical investigation of the performance of each of these choices contrasted to NCPs. The data set for the second experiment, on the other hand, analyzes the task of navigating a mobile robot around obstacles in its route. NCP as well as the three RNN variations are referred to as Deep RNN, LSTM, and GRU in the following tables and figures. The input data and a rectified linear unit activation function control our model, which comprises of two layers of one of the RNN and NCP block variations (ReLU). Furthermore, despite the fact that we utilized the Adam optimizer, Adadelata optimizer studies produced identical findings. We construct the length of a time series in which the input feature is sinusoidal and cosine waves for synthetic sinusoidal training examples. A sine wave with double the frequency of the input signal is the intended output signal. The networks were built in Python with the Keras library and Theano as the backend framework. Keras supports RNN layer classes including SimpleRNN, LSTM, and GRU, as well as neural circuit policies (NCP), the latter of which may be explicitly implemented. It's worth noting that retaining the very last layer as an RNN isn't optimal; it has to have a single entity because we're forecasting a time series, which requires an unique output value each time step. Have one unit, on the other hand, indicates that the concealed state is only a single integer. That's not a lot, and it's certainly not all that helpful; therefore, the RNN will largely utilize the hidden layer of the previous recurrent layers to transfer over all the information it needs from time step to time step, and it won't use the hidden layer of the final layer very much. Furthermore, because the *tanh* activation function is used by default in the SimpleRNN, LSTM, and GRU layers, the predicted values must fall between -1 and 1 . However, if we wish to utilize a different activation method for each of these reasons, replacing the output layer with a dense layer could be beneficial: it would operate somewhat quicker, have about the same accuracy, and enable us to use any output activation function we desire. `return sequences=True` should be removed from the last recurrent layer in this situation. The RNN layer of units is followed by a dense layer (where the activation is the element-wise activation function passed as the activation argument) of both synthetic sinusoidal training data and the navigation of a mobile robot dataset to forecast the path, except the NCP, as we can set motor neurons (output neurons) into one when we design the NCP wiring. The Adam optimization is used as the choice of optimizer that is known to adapt the learning rate for each of the parameters. Now, let's look at how our models performed on the first training data. We begin by creating a synthetic sinusoidal training sequence. On the synthetic sequence we constructed, we compared our three types of recurrent neural network (RNN) variations to the neural circuit policies (NCPs) model.

Fig. 1 Synthetic sinusoidal training example

The sequence time series created for each model is 48 in length. We ran various iterations for each scenario at the same constant base learning rate of 1e-3. Fig. 1 shows our training examples and Fig. 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 show the outcomes of our tests, with a summary in Table I below.

Fig. 2 Training loss of Deep RNN on synthetic sinusoidal training example at a constant base learning rate of 1e-3

Fig. 3 Training loss of LSTM on synthetic sinusoidal training example at a constant base learning rate of 1e-3

Fig. 4 Training loss of GRU on synthetic sinusoidal training example at a constant base learning rate of 1e-3

Fig. 5 Training loss of NCP on synthetic sinusoidal training example at a constant base learning rate of 1e-3

Fig. 6 Comparison of all four models

Table I: Synthetic sinusoidal training example: loss (%) performance and sparsity of different models using the same constant base learning rates over 400 epochs

Architecture	Loss	Sparsity %
RNN	8.1472e-04	100
LSTM	3.7735e-05	100
GRU	6.2128e-05	100
NCP	3.9907e-04	81.25

All four RNN versions (SimpleRNN, LSTM, GRU, and NCP) appear to have equivalent loss performance over the same constant base learning rate, according to Table I and Figs. 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6. SimpleRNN and NCP had similar results to LSTM and GRU, which also had similar results between themselves. The addition of more epochs is unlikely to improve performance between these variations after around 80 epochs. It should be noted that NCP can achieve comparable performance with 81 percent sparsity in this experiment, which is important for efficiency. In specific applications and/or available resources, computational expenditure reductions may play a role in selecting one variation over the others. Next, let's have a look at how our models performed on the second training set. We start by downloading a dataset that focuses at the challenge of navigating a robotic vehicle around obstacles. A Sick LMS 1xx laser rangefinder (LiDAR) installed on the robot provides input data. The driving heading is produced as a variable in the domain [-1,+1], with -1 corresponding to turning left, 0 to going straight, and +1 corresponding to turning right. Manually directing the robot through the barriers on 29 distinct tracks was used to acquire supervised training examples. On this dataset, we evaluated the neural circuit policies (NCPs) model to our three types of recurrent neural network (RNN) variants. Fig. 7 shows our training examples and Fig. 8, 9, 10, and 11 show the outcomes of our tests, with a summary in Table II below

Fig. 7 Navigating a mobile robot dataset

The input data is delivered as a time series, with a full laser rangefinder scan at every time step. The LiDAR scan is then sent into the feedforward section of the network, which generates a 32-dimensional latent representation of the current input. The SimpleRNN, LSTM, GRU, and NCP change their internal state and output prediction using this latent feature as input.

Fig. 8 Training and validation loss of Deep RNN on navigating a mobile robot dataset at a constant base learning of $1e-3$

Fig. 9 Training and validation loss of LSTM on navigating a mobile robot dataset at a constant base learning of $1e-3$

Fig. 10 Training and validation loss of GRU on navigating a mobile robot dataset at a constant base learning of $1e-3$

Fig. 11 Training and validation loss of NCP on navigating a mobile robot dataset at a constant base learning of $1e-3$

Table II: Navigating a mobile robot dataset: loss (%) performance and number of parameters of different models using the same constant base learning rates over 20 epochs.

Architecture	Loss before training(validation set)	Loss after training(training set)	Number of parameters
RNN	0.4031	0.1222	20,191
LSTM	0.1882	0.1006	60,223
GRU	0.2327	0.0957	46,975
NCP	0.2050	0.1229	23,715

We used a fixed base learning rate of $1e-3$ over 20 epochs to train the dataset on SimpleRNN, LSTM, GRU, and NCP. We also use 32-dimensional SimpleRNN, LSTM, GRU, and NCP in the training, with a batch size of 32. Both the training and validation losses of SimpleRNN and NCP fluctuated when employing a constant base learning rate of $1e-3$ (see Fig. 8, 11), but the losses of GRU and LSTM were more consistent (see Fig. 9, 10). Table II summarizes the loss rate findings, which reveal that SimpleRNN, LSTM, GRU, and NCP all perform similarly on the training set. However, the loss of the SimpleRNN on the validation set before training was the highest among the other three. Table II also shows how many parameters each has.

4. Conclusion

The experiments on the variants Deep RNN, LSTM, GRU and NCP have demonstrated that their loss performance is comparable on two example sequence lengths. One sequence was generated from the synthetic sinusoidal training example and one from the navigating a robot dataset. When we experimented on the synthetic sinusoidal training example, SimpleRNN and NCP showed similar results, while LSTM and GRU showed better results than the former two. However, in terms of sparsity, NCP was 81% while all others were a full 100%. Therefore, we can conclude that NCPs can achieve similar results to the other three famous models with less computational expense. Before the training, when we experimented on the navigating a robot dataset, we evaluated our model on the validation set. NCPs showed better results over SimpleRNN and GRU, but they were not as good as LSTM. On the other hand, after training, they showed a similar loss overall. The purpose of this research is to compare the performance of Deep RNN, LSTM, and GRU to the NCP, which has fewer parameters and sparsity than the other types of RNN and hence requires less computing resources. More experimental assessments with constant learning rates and training for a larger number of epochs can be done to confirm performance over a larger domain and reduce loss. We suggest that the NCP version be compared on a larger number of datasets in order to obtain more empirical proof of their performance.

References

- [1]. Chris Nicholson. A Beginner's Guide to LSTMs and Recurrent Neural Networks. <https://skymind.ai/wiki/lstm>. Accessed: 06 November 2019. 2019.
- [2]. S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long short-term memory," vol. 9, pp. 1735–80, 12 1997.
- [3]. J. Chung, Ç. Gülçehre, K. Cho, and Y. Bengio, "Empirical evaluation of gated recurrent neural networks on sequence modeling," CoRR, vol. abs/1412.3555, 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1412.3555>
- [4]. N. Kalchbrenner and P. Blunsom, "Recurrent Continuous Translation Models," *Emnlp*, no. October, pp. 1700–1709, 2013.
- [5]. S. Venugopalan, M. Rohrbach, J. Donahue, R. Mooney, T. Darrell, and K. Saenko, "Sequence to sequence - Video to text," in Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision, vol. 2015 International Conference on Computer Vision, ICCV 2015, 2015, pp. 4534–4542.
- [6]. X. SHI, Z. Chen, H. Wang, D.-Y. Yeung, W.-k. Wong, and W.-c. WOO, "Convolutional lstm network: A machine learning approach for precipitation nowcasting," in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 28, C. Cortes, N. D. Lawrence, D. D. Lee, M. Sugiyama, and R. Garnett, Eds. Curran Associates, Inc., 2015, pp. 802–810.
- [7]. A. van den Oord, N. Kalchbrenner, and K. Kavukcuoglu, "Pixel recurrent neural networks," CoRR, vol. abs/1601.06759, 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1601.06759>
- [8]. B. Yu, H. Yin, and Z. Zhu, "Spatio-temporal graph convolutional neural network: A deep learning framework for traffic forecasting," CoRR, vol. abs/1709.04875, 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1709.04875>
- [9]. Lechner, M., Hasani, R., Amini, A., Henzinger, T. A., Rus, D., & Grosu, R. (2020). Neural circuit policies enabling auditable autonomy. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 2(10), 642–652.
- [10]. Yamak, P.T., Yujian, L., Gadosey, P.K.: A comparison between ARIMA, LSTM, and GRU for time series forecasting. In: Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Algorithms, Computing and Artificial Intelligence. pp. 49–55. ACM (2019)
- [11]. Hüsken, M., Stagge, P.: Recurrent neural networks for time series classification. *Neurocomputing* 50, 223–235 (2003)
- [12]. Mallhotra, P., TV, V., Vig, L., Agarwal, P., Shroff, G.: TimeNet: Pre-trained deep recurrent neural network for time series classification. In: Proceedings of 25th European Symposium on Artificial Neural Networks (2017)

- [13]. Cahuantzi, Roberto, Xinye Chen, and Stefan Güttel. "A comparison of LSTM and GRU networks for learning symbolic sequences." arXiv preprint arXiv:2107.02248 (2021).
- [14]. Greff, K., Srivastava, R.K., Koutník, J., Steunebrink, B.R., Schmidhuber, J.: LSTM: A search space odyssey. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems* 28, 2222–2232 (2017)
- [15]. Dey, Rahul, and Fathi M. Salem. "Gate-variants of gated recurrent unit (GRU) neural networks." 2017 IEEE 60th international midwest symposium on circuits and systems (MWSCAS). IEEE, 2017.
- [16]. Schmidt, R. M. (2019). Recurrent neural networks (rnns): A gentle introduction and overview. arXiv preprint arXiv:1912.05911.
- [17]. Yoshua Bengio, Patrice Simard, and Paolo Frasconi, "Learning Long-Term Dependencies with Gradient Descent Is Difficult," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks* 5, no. 2 (1994).
- [18]. Sepp Hochreiter and Jürgen Schmidhuber. "Long Short-term Memory". In: *Neural computation* 9 (Dec. 1997), pp. 1735–80.
- [19]. Haşım Sak et al., "Long Short-Term Memory Based Recurrent Neural Network Architectures for Large Vocabulary Speech Recognition," arXiv preprint arXiv:1402.1128 (2014).
- [20]. Wojciech Zaremba et al., "Recurrent Neural Network Regularization," arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.2329 (2014).
- [21]. Nicholson, C. (2019). A beginner's guide to lstms and recurrent neural networks. Skymind. Saatavissa: <https://skymind.ai/wiki/lstm>. Hakupäivä, 6, 2019.
- [22]. Cho, K., Van Merriënboer, B., Gulcehre, C., Bahdanau, D., Bougares, F., Schwenk, H., & Bengio, Y. (2014). Learning phrase representations using RNN encoder-decoder for statistical machine translation. arXiv preprint arXiv:1406.1078.
- [23]. Greff, K., Srivastava, R. K., Koutník, J., Steunebrink, B. R., & Schmidhuber, J. (2016). LSTM: A search space odyssey. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*, 28(10), 2222-2232.
- [24]. Chung, J., Gulcehre, C., Cho, K., and Bengio, Y. Empirical Evaluation of Gated Recurrent Neural Networks on Sequence Modeling. arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.3555, 2014.
- [25]. Cho, K., Van Merriënboer, B., Bahdanau, D., & Bengio, Y. (2014). On the properties of neural machine translation: Encoderdecoder approaches. arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.1259.
- [26]. Hasani, R. M., Lechner, M., Amini, A., Rus, D., & Grosu, R. (2018). Liquid time-constant recurrent neural networks as universal approximators. arXiv preprint arXiv:1811.00321.

